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To search an exact word(s) use quotation marks, e.g. "hospital" finds hospital; hospital (no quotation marks) finds hospital and hospitals; pay finds paid, pays, paying, payed) Highlight orphan lines

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|----|--|--|
| 1. | <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 2px 5px;">#1</div> <p>(torso or trunk or back or abdomen or pelvis or thorax) and (muscle near/3 strength):ti,ab,kw or ((trunk or core or postural) near/3 (strenght* or stabili*)):ti,ab,kw or ((muscle near/3 composition) and (balance or "functional performance" or (falls and (association or relationship or correlation)))):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)</p> | <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 2px 5px;">1036</div> |
| 2. | <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 2px 5px;">#2</div> <p>((aged or elder*) near/3 (person* or patient* or man or men or woman or women or people)):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)</p> | <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 2px 5px;">58133</div> |
| 3. | <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 2px 5px;">#3</div> <p>((motor near/3 control) or (neuromuscular near/3 control) or (motor near/3 skill) or (cognit* near/3 motor) or (cognitive near/3 trunk) or feedback or (swiss near/3 ball)) and (training or exercise* or therapy or rehabilitation or mov*):ti,ab,kw or (cognit* or propriocept* or coordinative or voluntary or deliberat* or intentional* or willful or wilful or purpose* or designed or planned or intended) near/6 (training or exercise* or therapy or rehabilitation or mov*):ti,ab,kw or (sensorimotor or sensorymotor or (sensory near/3 motor) or videogames or exergames or "dual task" or proprioception or (coordinat* near/3 muscle*)):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)</p> | <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 2px 5px;">33014</div> |
| 4. | <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 2px 5px;">#4</div> <p>(exercise or physical near/3 therapy or physiotherapy or pilates):ti,ab,kw or ((muscle or strength or resistance or balance) near/3 (training or therapy)):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)</p> | <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 2px 5px;">60695</div> |
| 5. | <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 2px 5px;">#5</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 2px 5px;">#1 and #2 and #3 and #4 Enter terms for search</div> | <div style="border: 1px solid black; display: inline-block; padding: 2px 5px;">31</div> |